

New Additive manufacturing Heat Exchanger for Aeronautic

ITD/IADP/TA : LPA IADP
Grant Agreement No 785520

Deliverable Reference Number: D4.2

Combined hot-cold channel Tests, Results and Analysis

Lead participant: IVKDF
Contributing participant(s): IVKDF

July 2021

Type		
R	Document, report	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, etc.	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (incl. Commission Services)	

APPROVAL

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CHANGE LOG

Description	Issue	Revision	Date

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The WP4 is dedicated to the Realization of aerothermal and mechanical tests of elementary component of the CHX on dedicated test facilities by means of advanced measurement techniques. Two main facilities will be designed to test two types of elementary components: single channel elements, and combined hot-cold elements.

This report summarizes the work done on the tasks T4.4, T4.5, and T4.6 dedicated to the measurements of the combined hot-cold channel elements. The first task consisted in designing the facility dedicated to aerothermal measurements to be performed on combined hot-cold modules. The second task consisted in instrumenting the modules. The focus was on measuring inlet temperature, outlet temperature profiles, but also the mass flow rate and the pressure drop caused by the sample. Finally, the third task consisted in performing the experimental tests on the hot-cold modules. Originally 4 modules were planned; 2 in Inconel and 2 in Aluminium; one being composed by the optimum structures deduced from the numerical study described in the deliverable D3.1, and one where the fins were evolving from the inlet to the outlet of the sample. However, the evolution in case of Aluminum was not found interesting and therefore, only one sample was tested for this material. For all tests, experimental data were processed and analyzed. Correlations of pressure drop, fanning factor, as well as efficiency and overall heat transfer are proposed.

The second chapter of this deliverable is dedicated to the description of the experimental facility, designed and built during T4.4, as well as the instrumentation designed and implemented in T4.5. The third chapter is dedicated to the aeraulic characterization of both the inlet flow, and the different samples, where the outlet velocity profiles, but also the evolution of pressure in dimensional, scaled, and non-dimensional forms is described. The fourth chapter is dedicated to the thermal characterization of the samples, from the investigation of the heat flux exchanged between the hot and cold side, to the outlet temperature profiles. This chapter has also investigated the thermal efficiency and NTU correlations, as well as looked at the overall heat transfer coefficient for the different samples. Similarly to the previous chapter, correlations are developed to predict the thermal performances. Finally, before the conclusions, a chapter dedicated to the uncertainty analysis of the different measured quantities is added.

Chapter 2

Experimental Setup

In this chapter, the experimental facility which was utilized for the investigation of the three combined hot-cold channels is described with its main components. Measurement instruments are introduced in detail together with their calibrations. Additionally, the description of the CHX samples is also provided, as well as the experimental matrix and test philosophy.

2.1 Experimental Facility

Figure 2.1: Schematic representation of the experimental facility.

The facility dedicated to aerothermal performance of the combined hot-cold channel has been designed and built around March 2020. A schematic representation of the experimental facility is given in Figure 2.2. The facility consists in a cross with the horizontal section being dedicated to the cold side, while the vertical section is dedicated to the hot side. The hot side can reach 50 g/s at 300°C thanks to the IVKDF compressed air system as well as a 17kW thermal resistance. The cold side can reach 50 g/s either at ambient temperature, or at temperature as low as -30°C due to a mixing of the ambient air with liquid nitrogen. Each section consists of 1m length upstream and 0.5m length downstream the sample. The dimensions of these section are consistent with the sample dimension. All sections are insulated, except for the inlet section of the cold side. Finally, a heat exchanger is connected to the exit of the cold section to pre-heat the incoming air before entering the thermal resistance. More information about the different components will be provided in the following sections.

Figure 2.2: Picture of the experimental facility.

2.1.1 Electrical Heater

The air flow for the hot side is heated up to $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ degrees depending on the required operating conditions of hot-cold channel. To be able to do that, one Vulcanic electrical (resistance) heater is utilized together with its control panel. Installed electrical heater has a nominal power of 17kW and it can resist up to 5 barG as operating pressure. Maximum allowable temperature is $360\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ but control panel allow $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ maximum.

Additionally, inlet temperature of the electrical heat is measured with a K type thermocouple to calculate heat transfer occurred in electrical heater.

(a) Schematic representation of Plate Heat Exchanger (PHE) [1]

(b) Pre-heater PHE

Figure 2.3: PHE used as pre-heater in the facility

2.1.2 Preheater

To reduce the electrical power needed to heat up the air on the hot side, the air from the cold side outlet section of the hot-cold channel is introduced in a plate heat exchanger (PHE) that pre-heat the air before entering the electrical resistance. Plate heat exchangers consists of two pipelines for each side in counter flow configuration together with numerous plates in having gasket design which enables air flow in between plates. Kelvion Brazed type GBS760L-40 PHE is utilized in the experimental facility as preheated consists of AISI316 plates and copper as a solder material. With a capability of 45kW of heat transfer, it consists of 40 plates and 5 m^2 of heat exchange area. Main components of PHE is illustrated [1] and PHE utilized as "preheater" is given in Figure 2.3.

2.1.3 LN_2 mixing tank

In order to conduct experiments which have inlet temperature lower than ambient conditions for cold side inlet port, liquid nitrogen (LN_2) tank is utilized. Liquid nitrogen and pressured air in ambient conditions are being mixed in a mixing tank designed in VKI. Exhaust port of the mixing tank connects to the system and mass flow rate. Thus, total mass flow rate is measured after mixing happens. Schematic representation of the LN_2 is shown in 2.4

Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of LN_2 mixing tank.

2.2 CHX Samples

Three hot-cold channels were tested in the frame of task T4.6; two made of Inconel material (IN718), and one made of Aluminum (AS7G06). All channels were designed by Themisth and produced by AddUp.

The design for the channel involves cross flow configuration. In addition for each stream, namely cold and hot sides, there are 2 large and one small passage for Inconel samples, and 1 large and 1 small passage for Aluminum sample. The larger channel(s) have two times of the height of the small passage. In every passage, offset fins have been utilized. The shape of the fin is called chevron fin which has a 45 degree angle with each contact surface. The fin design results in a V shaped, vertical fins along the CHX. Schematic representation of the chevron fins are given in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Offset chevron fin design used in CHX design.

2.2.1 First Inconel Sample (IN718-1)

First CHX sample includes 86 fins at hot side and 34 fins for cold side at each passage. As discussed before there are two large and one smaller passage for each side. The fin design and related dimensions for the first IN718 CHX sample is tabulated in Table 2.1 for the large passage. The small passage is similar, but with the height halved. The hydraulic diameter and exchange area are listed in 2.2.

	Length (l) [mm]	Height (h) [mm]	Spacing (s) [mm]	Thickness (t) [mm]
Hot side	4	4.5	0.917	0.3
Cold Side	1.75	7.65	2.417	0.3

Table 2.1: Fin dimensions of the first CHX sample.

Hydraulic diameter in between the fins is chosen as the characteristic length for the calculations. Since there is a curvature at the top and bottom of the fins, hydraulic diameter for each side is calculated by computing the cross sectional area and perimeter of the region in between two sequential fins. The region of interest for hydraulic diameter calculations is shown in Figure 2.6. The printing of this channel had to be adapted as a previous version with lower fin thickness could not be achieved. But a slight increase of fin thickness and the curvature on top and bottom of the fins allowed a proper realization of the channel. The only defect for this sample was created during the removal of the printing supports, where cuts were made into the outlet walls in between fins. This was therefore corrected by filling the space with thermal paste. Some pictures of the sample can be observed in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.6: Region for hydraulic diameter calculations.

Figure 2.7: First Inconel (IN718-1) sample.

	Exchange area [mm ²]	Hydraulic diameter [mm]
Large Hot side	90986	1.57
Small Hot side	50463	1.36
Large Cold side	87591	3.82
Small Cold side	52470	3.07

Table 2.2: Hydraulic diameter and Exchange area for the Inconel 1 channel

2.2.2 Second Sample (IN718-2)

The second CHX sample has the exact fin design for the hot side; being two large channels and one half height channel. The cold side also consists of two large channels and one half height channel. On the other hand, fin geometry of cold side is linearly changing along CHX sample. Fin spacing and the thickness of the fins differ in between inlet and outlet sections of cold side. Dimensions regarding the fin

designs are tabulated in Table 2.3 and 2.4. In terms of printing, one big issues happened as the small hot channel where the powder could not be properly eliminated. This resulted in a blocked channel, as shown in figure 2.8

	Length (l) [mm]	Height (h) [mm]	Spacing (s) [mm]	Thickness (t) [mm]
Hot side	4	4.5	0.917	0.3
Cold Side (inlet)	1.75	7.65	2.417	0.3
Cold Side (outlet)	1.75	7.65	3.64	0.4

Table 2.3: Fin dimensions of the second CHX sample.

Figure 2.8: Tomographic image of (IN718-2) sample.

	Exchange area [mm ²]	Hydraulic diameter [mm]
Large Hot side	91568	1.57
Small Hot side	50765	1.36
Large Cold side (outlet)	79677	3.82 (5.16)
Small Cold side (outlet)	49421	3.07 (3.8)

Table 2.4: Hydraulic diameter and Exchange area for the Inconel 2 channel

2.2.3 Aluminium Sample (AS7G06)

In addition to the Inconel channels, one Aluminium channel has been investigated as well. Compared to the Inconel samples, Aluminium sample has larger hot side channel dimensions in terms of spacing of fins and the height of the fins. Also, Aluminium channel has only one large channel and one half-height channel for each side, compared to two for Inconel. Consequently, AS7G06 sample exhibits higher hydraulic diameter and lesser pressure drops are expected. Dimensions of the sample are summarized in Table 2.5, as well as 2.6. In terms, of printing, no major issue was detected on this sample, except for the flanges which were slightly distorted, and a few distorted fins on the outlet, as shown in 2.9.

	Length (l) [mm]	Height (h) [mm]	Spacing (s) [mm]	Thickness (t) [mm]
Hot side	6	7	1.2	0.25
Cold Side	4.35	8	2.75	0.25

Table 2.5: Fin dimensions of the second CHX sample.

(a) Cold side

(b) Hot side

(c) Complete channel

Figure 2.9: Aluminum hot-cold channel sample

	Exchange area [mm ²]	Hydraulic diameter [mm]
Large Hot side	114499	2.086
Small Hot side	64354	1.84
Large Cold side	73476	4.27
Small Cold side	44155	3.45

Table 2.6: Hydraulic diameter and Exchange area for the Aluminum channel

2.3 Instrumentation

There are 4 different pressure transducers, 38 thermocouples and 2 mass flow meter are used during the experiments. In this section, each instrument type together with calibration details and important

aspects related with measurements will be introduced. In terms of position, the pressure and temperature are measured upstream and downstream of the sample, on both channels, according to figure 2.10. The pressure is a static pressure measurement taken from the channel wall, while the temperature is a point measurement taken at the center of the channel.

(a) Aluminum Sample

(b) Inconel Samples

Figure 2.10: Position of upstream and downstream instrumentation

2.3.1 Pressure measurements

Pressure at inlet and outlet ports of both streams were measured by using AMS 5812 type pressure transducers together with 6 channel pressure sensor amplifier for AMS type pressure transducers.

Differential type pressure transducers were used. There is a linear relation in between the uncertainty of a pressure transducer and pressure range. Thus, depending on the pressure level, different type of pressure transducers are selected to be able to optimize measurement range and sensitivity at same time. The range of sensors depending on the sample is detailed in Table 2.7. . Voltage reading for transducers were recorded by using data acquisition system (2.3.5).

Calibration of the pressure transducers were conducted by using the pressure calibrator devices.

Sample	Side		Range [Psi]
AS7G06	Hot	ΔP	5
AS7G06	Cold	ΔP	0.8
In718-1	Hot	In	5
In718-1	Hot	Out	0.075
In718-1	Cold	In	0.8
In718-1	Cold	Out	0.15
In718-2	Hot	In	5
In718-2	Hot	Out	0.075
In718-2	Cold	In	0.8
In718-2	Cold	Out	0.15

Table 2.7: Pressure sensor details

2.3.2 Velocity measurements

Velocity measurements were conducted with servo-loop hot wire anemometer of $5\mu\text{m}$ diameter tungsten wire. The Wire itself has 1.0033 ohm resistance and hot wire probe has 1.9 ohm of total resistance. Additionally, overheat ratio is lower than 1.6 and resistance of the hot wire should be in the correct range. One of the direct output is connected to the wire by using a 5m transmission cable which is part of the Wheatstone bridge balance.

Oscilloscope is used to observe the results of square test during dynamic calibration. L and Q knobs were optimized to see better time response with higher response frequency. Results of the dynamic calibration is given in Figure 2.11, performed at xx m/s in ...

As can be seen from the Figure 2.11, results are oscillatory. The signal is neither filtered or amplified, thus the oscillation is addressed to not using a filter together with electrical noise. As a result of dynamic calibration, 89.525 μs of response time and 5.529 kHz frequency response is achieved. Regarding that, in accordance with To respect Nyquist criteria, given in Eqn. 2.1, the sampling frequency when acquiring the signal during experiments shall be more than two times superior to the maximum frequency contained in the signal.

$$f_s > 2f_{max} \quad (2.1)$$

For this experiment, the f_s has been set to 15 kHz with respect to Nyquist criterion. The acquisition time is chosen to minimize the measurement uncertainty as given below:

$$N = f_s \times t_{acquisition} > \left(\frac{2 \times z_{1-\alpha/2} \times \sigma_x}{\Delta x} \right)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.11: Square wave test result.

where σ_x expressed the standard deviation of the velocity, Δx is relative uncertainty, $z_{1-a/2}$ is the width of the confidence interval. For velocity measurements ($x=U$), the relative uncertainty is defined by the ratio between the uncertainty of the measured values and the mean value. Thus, it is possible to relate the Eq.2.2 with the turbulence intensity. Finally, a relation between the relative uncertainty of the velocity measurement for 95% of confidence interval ($\Delta x'$) and the turbulence intensity is obtained. The last is shown in the Eq.2.3.

$$N > \left(\frac{3.92 \times TI}{\Delta x'} \right)^2 \quad (2.3)$$

Due to feasibility, 10 seconds of acquisition period was adopted, corresponding to 150k of samples. Therefore, the resultant relative uncertainty in mean velocity is 0.036 % with respect to 10 % of turbulence intensity. In order to conduct static calibration, jet nozzle type calibrator was utilized. Static calibration have been repeated in the beginning of measurements. Ambient temperature was also recorded together with static calibration. Results of static calibration are illustrated in Figure 2.12 for one day. Summary of the static calibrations are given in table 2.8.

Figure 2.12: Static Calibration results at 16 C condition

During measurements, one dimensional traverse system is used to change hot wire position precisely. Sample hot wire measurement is shown in Figure 2.13.

Traverse system is controlled with EPOS 2 motor controller. EPOS 2 has a graphical user interface (GUI) encoded in LabVIEW. Operator have to define gear ratio and box ID number in GUI to maintain sufficient communication and accurate control for positioning of hot wire. During hot wire measurements, 0.1 mm spacing in between two sequential measurements are preferred near to wall vicinity to capture boundary layer precisely, than after 0.2 to 0.5mm of displacements have preferred depending on the position.

$$U = p_1x^4 + p_2x^3 + p_3x^2 + p_4x + p_5$$

Temperature [C]	p-1	p-2	p-3	p-4	p-5	R ²	RMSE
16	-21.28	185.9	-565.3	727.6	-338	0.9993	0.1324
18.2	-4.266	39.51	-97.92	73.28	0.6898	0.9996	0.1317
19.5	4.08	-20.01	55.57	-94.15	64.06	0.9996	0.12
19.8	-2.745	35.79	-115.5	139.5	-55.62	0.9994	0.1553
22.1	5.151	-20.42	31.49	-27.48	13.88	0.9999	0.0898

Table 2.8: Summary of static calibration for hot wire measurements.

Figure 2.13: Velocity Measurement.

2.3.3 Mass flow rate measurements

In this experimental study, DVH Series Vortex Flowmeter for each side have been utilized. Working temperature range is -40 to 400 C and promises valid measurements for experiments with uncertainty as $\pm 0.2\%$ of mass flow rate. The measuring principle is based on the von Karman vortex theory. A specially designed bluff body is located in the flow path. With specific flow velocities, vortices are generated by the presence of the bluff body. These vortices generate small pressure differences in the wake, that is directly related with the frequency of the vortices and proportional to the flow velocity. Then, the mass flow rate is calculated by measured values of pressure, temperature and flow rate. Every measured value have its own calibration. Thus, vortex type mass flow meter measures mass flow rate indirectly. In-built pressure, temperature and density calibration curves are given in equations 2.4-2.7, respectively.

$$P[\text{barg}] = 250 \times I[A] - 1 \quad (2.4)$$

$$T[C] = 5000 \times I[A] - 60 \quad (2.5)$$

$$Q[\text{m}^3/\text{h}] = 31250 \times I[A] - 125 \quad (2.6)$$

Overall mass flow rate calibration is as:

$$\dot{m}[\text{g/s}] = 3750 \times I[A] - 15 \quad (2.7)$$

2.3.4 Temperature measurements

In experimental facility, 38 K type thermocouples are utilized to investigate heat transfer in detail. Schematic representation of thermocouple orientation is given below.

Figure 2.14: Schematic representation of thermocouples in the facility.

As can be seen from Figure 2.14, there are 4 thermocouples that take temperature measurement from the inlet and outlet sections of hot and cold sides, with the exact dimensions listed in Figure 2.10. Additionally, rakes consisting for each of 14 thermocouples are positioned at each outlet section to understand the temperature profile on the outlet precisely and to obtain data for numerical validation studies. Additionally, there are two thermocouples at the inlet of the electrical heater, and at the outlet of the preheater to measure the performance of these elements. Thermocouple rakes and their identifiers are given in Figure 2.16 for the Aluminum sample, while Figure 2.17 and 2.18 are providing the same information for the two Inconel samples respectively. Finally, all samples have also 6 thermocouples positioned at mid height in the smaller hot channel, as shown in Figure 2.15.

For acquisition 3 different NI-9213 type acquisition board were utilized. In-built calibration curve of LABview have been utilized for thermocouple measurements [2]. Calibration curve for K type thermocouple is 9^{th} order polynomial as implemented in the module.

2.3.5 Data Acquisition System

Five NI (National Instruments) data acquisition boards were utilized to record measured data at computer. Connection to computer was maintained with a USB cable. Three of them were used for thermocouples while other two have used to acquire data from mass flow meters and pressure transducer.

Data acquisition board for mass flow rate measurement is working with the range of $\pm 20mA$ while other boards works with $\pm 10V$ range.

2.4 Experimental Matrix

To be able to maintain an adequate aerothermal characterization of CHX samples, effects of main parameters defining operating conditions have been investigated. Parameters that have been considered are:

- Mass flow rate of hot side

Figure 2.15: Thermocouples located inside the small hot fin channel

Figure 2.16: Position and naming of thermocouples for the hot and cold outlet of Aluminum sample

- Inlet temperature of hot side
- Mass flow rate of cold side
- Inlet temperature of cold side

Figure 2.17: Position and naming of thermocouples for the hot and cold outlet of the Inconel-1 sample

Figure 2.18: Position and naming of thermocouples for the hot and cold outlet of the Inconel-2 sample

As known, temperature and pressure are defining the most of the thermophysical properties that are affecting heat and momentum transfer. Thus investigating the effects of temperature is essential for this research. Three different temperature scenarios are considered in experimental campaigns. They are: $150^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{Ambient}$, $300^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{Ambient}$ and $150^{\circ}\text{C}/-30^{\circ}\text{C}$. For most of the experiments ambient temperature was measured in the range of $20 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Hot side inlet temperature values were controlled by the control

panel of electrical heater. Cold side temperature of -30°C condition was also controlled by setting the mass flow rates of liquid nitrogen and air. Ambient conditions were not controlled but temperature values for each measurement were recorded and evaluated during post process of data.

The limiting factor for the mass flow rate was the mass flow meter range during the campaigns. Mass flow meter could be able to measure in between 15 to 50 g/s. Thus same limits are respected while conducting measurements. It should be noted that lower than this limit, relation in between mass flow rate and pressure difference can be used and lower mass flow rates can be achieved by the pressure drop information. There are two different strategies were opted to determine mass flow rates for each side:

- Iso- \dot{m} approach: Mass flow rates for each side are considered independent from each other. This approach is independent from the thermophysical properties and temperature.
- Iso-Reynolds approach: Mass flow rates were considered dependent. Mass flow rates are determined in a way that Reynolds number for the hot and cold sides are identical. Ratio between mass flow rates for hot and cold sides can be written as given below.

$$\dot{m}_{hot} = \dot{m}_{cold} \left(\frac{D_{h,cold}}{\mu_{cold} A_{cs,cold}} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{hot} A_{cs,hot}}{D_{h,hot}} \right) \quad (2.8)$$

Since relation depends on the viscosities, mass flow rate values differ for different set of temperatures for both sides as well.

As an example, mass flow rate for the first CHX sample at 150°C /Ambient conditions are given in Figure 2.19 below. As can be seen, there is a linear relation between the mass flow rates for hot and cold sides for Iso-Re approach. The slope of this line is dependent on temperature as well. Thus, for different set of temperature, target \dot{m} values for Iso-Re approach is changing in accordance to the change in thermophysical properties.

2.5 Nomenclature

To analyze the results, several quantities will be needed and are defined here. The Reynolds number is an important quantity to propose a non-dimensional form of the mass flow rate, and is defined in equation 2.10. The Reynolds number requires a definition of the hydraulic diameter, which for the hot-cold channels is not straightforward since there are 2 heights of fins. So it was decided to define according of equation 4.14, using the area and perimeter to account for the shape of the fins towards the walls, and where i is either 1 for Aluminum samples and 2 for Inconel. In the Reynolds number, the velocity is obtained by dividing the mass flow rate by the fluid inlet density and the inlet cross sectional area.

$$D_h = \frac{4 * (i * A_{big} + A_{small})}{i * P_{big} + P_{small}} \quad (2.9)$$

$$Re = \frac{\rho D_h U}{\mu} = \frac{\dot{m} D_h}{A_{cs} \mu} \quad (2.10)$$

Figure 2.19: Mass flow rates tested with first CHX sample at 150/Ambient conditions.

Chapter 3

Aeraulic characterization

In this chapter, the experimental results concerning the velocity distribution and the pressure evolution are presented and discussed. Additionally, given results are investigated in the perspective of characterization.

For clarity, results related to momentum and heat transfer are discussed separately. In addition, three different samples were compared by their performance in different aspects.

It should be noted that uncertainty bars introduced in the results are derived in accordance with uncertainty quantification in Chapter 5.

3.1 Hot wire measurements

Hot wire measurements were performed to characterize the inlet velocity profiles, to be used as boundary conditions for the numerical simulations performed by the NATHENA partners. Motivation behind hot wire measurements are also to investigate the inlet flow development as well as how is the flow distributed at the outlet of the hot-cold channels. Since the dimensions of the rectangular pipelines are different for the Aluminum and Inconel samples, the inlet flow was characterized for both sizes.

Figure 3.1: Position of hot wire profiles

At each centerline, for several mass flow rates, velocity and turbulence intensity profiles are measured, according to nomenclature illustrated in Figure 3.1. All the results are non-dimensionnalized by the section height or width respectively for the transverse and longitudinal profiles. The velocity profile is scaled by the maximum velocity measured on the profile (except when the influence of the flow rate is shown), while the turbulence intensity is defined as the the rms of the fluctuations divided by the maximum velocity of the profile. First, the inlet profiles will be presented, then the outlet profiles will be investigated.

3.1.1 Inlet profiles

The inlet profiles were measured for the Aluminum only on the hot inlet channel. The effect of the inlet channel length was assessed on the longitudinal profile of the hot inlet for 40 g/s. As shown in Figure 3.2, a strong difference can be assessed between 1 section length, which is equivalent to a length of 500 mm, and 2 or 3 section lengths (respectively 1000 and 1500 mm). With 2 or 3 sections, the velocity profile is still slightly affected by the upstream bend by showing a little asymmetry while the turbulence intensity profile is rather symmetric.

Figure 3.2: Effect of flow development length: Aluminum, hot inlet, 40 g/s

The profiles were then measured at the hot inlet for two flow rates, as shown in Figure 3.3. The turbulence intensity is quite similar for both flow rates, with a mean value around 4-5 % at the center of the channel and peaks around 10-15%. A slight asymmetry on the transverse profile can be observed on the turbulence intensity profile.

Concerning the Inconel samples, the inlet profile for the 100x33.4 mm section was measured. First, the comparison of the longitudinal and transverse profiles for 1 or 2 section lengths (i.e. 500 or 1000 mm long) is assessed in Figure 3.4. It can be seen that having 1000 m length helps in having a more symmetrical profile and reduce the influence of the upstream bend (small asymmetry for 500 mm length on the inlet longitudinal profile)

The profiles were then measured for both hot and cold inlets at different flow rates: 20 g/s, 30 g/s, and 45 g/s. As shown in Figures 3.5 and 3.6, all profiles show a similar velocity longitudinal profile, increasing in velocity with the mass flow rate, and similar levels of turbulence intensity for the 3 flow rates, between 8 and 10%. However, the boundary layer thickness decreases as the flow rate increases. On the contrary, the boundary layer thickness does not evolve much with the flow rate for the transverse profiles.

Comparing both the hot and cold inlet for 45 g/s, it can be shown in Figure 3.7, the effect of the upstream bend is still slightly visible for the hot inlet longitudinal profile. Apart from that deviation, both profiles show similar velocity and turbulence intensity evolution.

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.3: Inlet velocity and turbulence intensity profiles: Hot Aluminum inlet

3.1.2 Outlet profiles

The outlet velocity profiles for the Aluminum sample were performed as Iso-Reynolds approach, i.e. with different mass flow rates to match the same inlet Reynolds number. The profiles of both hot and cold sides are compared in Figure 3.8.

The outlet profiles for both Inconel samples were measured both on the cold and hot sides, at 20 g/s. On the cold side profile illustrated in Figure 3.9, the longitudinal is not a flat as the inlet due to the presence of the fins, but shows approximately the same evolution, while for the transverse profile, the influence of the smaller fin height is clearly visible. For both profiles, the velocity going out of the sample has increased in turbulence intensity. The influence of the fin evolution is also visible in the transverse profiles, with a stronger asymmetry of the evolution for the second sample.

Looking at the hot side, similar conclusions can be drawn from Figure 3.10, which always show a

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.4: Effect of flow development length: Inconel hot inlet, 45 g/s

larger turbulence intensity on the outlet. However, the longitudinal profile show for both samples a slight increase in the velocity on the left side of the profile while the inlet flow was symmetric. The reason for this is unclear. On the transverse profile, the influence of the blocked fin channel is clearly visible, showing a transverse profile for the second sample with a larger velocity on one side while null velocity on the other side, confirming the blockage of the channel. As the velocity is a lot lower on the mid-height of the channel where the longitudinal profile is measured for the second Inconel sample, the resulting turbulence intensity is greatly increased.

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.5: Inlet velocity and turbulence intensity profiles: Hot Inconel inlet

3.2 Aeraulic Characterization

One of the key feature to assess when characterizing the hot-cold channel samples is the evolution of pressure drop. This evolution can be either dimensional (i.e. evolution of pressure drop with flow rate), or non-dimensional with the evolution of the fanning friction factor with Reynolds. In this section, both will be investigated.

Initially, pressure drop for each side are investigated separately. Figure 3.11, shows the pressure drops for the three samples, at the different temperature conditions tested.

As can be seen from Figure 3.11, hot side for each sample exhibits more pressure drop compared to the cold sides. The differences are more visible at higher mass flow rates since there is a quadratic relation in between mean velocity inside the channel and pressure drop which is also given in equation 3.3. This is a natural result of the fact that hot side channels are smaller in terms of hydraulic diameter compared to the cold side channels.

There is a clear relation between mass flow rate and pressure drop for each channel and it varies

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.6: Inlet velocity and turbulence intensity profiles: Cold Inconel inlet

with respect to the operating temperature. Since there is 150°C of difference in between two operating conditions for hot side, this occurrence is more visible at hot side as well especially at higher mass flow rates.

Effect of the operating temperature is directly related with the changes of thermophysical properties such as density and viscosity depending on the temperature. Thus from experimental results, we are observing indirect effects of the operating temperature on the pressure drops. In order to obtain one characteristic relation between mass flow rate and pressure drop, a normalization process is needed to prevent the effect of operating temperature on thermophysical properties. Force balance in the channels implies that the most dominant thermophysical property affecting the pressure drop is the dynamic viscosity since it is related with shear stresses. The normalization factor and normalized pressure drop definitions are therefore defined in equations 3.1 and 3.2 respectively. By applying normalization, all pressure drop measurements are falling into 1 curve similar to pressure the pressure drop at ambient conditions. Normalized pressure drops are also given in Figure 3.12.

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.7: Inlet velocity and turbulence intensity profiles: Comparison between hot and cold inlets, Inconel section, 45/gs

$$\sigma = \frac{\mu_{inlet}}{\mu_{ambient}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\overline{\Delta P} = \frac{\Delta P}{\sigma} \quad (3.2)$$

As can be seen from Figure 3.12, there is a quadratic relation between mass flow rate and normalized pressure drop for each side of each sample. AS7G06 results in lower normalized pressure drop compared to Inconel samples. This is due to the fact that for Aluminium samples, hot side channel dimensions are

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transverse profile

Figure 3.8: Outlet velocity profiles for Aluminum sample; cold side: 12 g/s, hot side: 37 g/s

larger compared to the Inconel samples. Thus pressure drops and normalized pressure drops are lower as expected from the theory. Also it should be noted that, the highest normalized pressure drops are observed at the hot side of IN718-2 even hot side channel dimensions are same for each Inconel samples. That can be addressed to the fact that the smaller channel at hot side of IN718-2 sample was blocked due to issues in the powder removal during the manufacturing.

By using this characterization, pressure drop values for a certain temperature and mass flow rate can be estimated in the range of experiments. Constants for the 2nd order polynomial relation are given in Table 3.1.

Another interesting analysis is to look closer at the comparison of the normalized pressure drop between the two Inconel samples. As the fins of the second sample have been optimized, the pressure drop for this sample should be decreased. However, as observed in ??, no clear difference can be observed between the respective two evolution of the normalized pressure drops.

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transversal profile

Figure 3.9: Outlet velocity profiles for Inconel, cold side: 20 g/s

$\overline{\Delta P} = p_0 + p_1 \dot{m} + p_2 \dot{m}^2$						
Sample	Side	p_0	p_1	p_2	R^2	RMSE [Pa]
AS7G06	Hot	-49.002	24.492	4.670	0.996	179.896
	Cold	164.735	-21.349	3.324	0.925	407.5993
IN718-1	Hot	-1441.653	205.757	7.314	0.9878	906.3485
	Cold	116.050	16.8	1.903	0.9511	310.5172
IN718-2	Hot	-110.428	126.619	14.296	0.9990	339.2915
	Cold	268.939	19.594	1.782	0.9720	217.6919

Table 3.1: Details of characterization for $\overline{\Delta P}$.

Considering the fanning factor is also essential for comparing of a given sample with other samples in the literature. The fanning factor is defined in equation 3.3.

$$f_F = \frac{\Delta P D_h}{2\rho U^2 L} \quad (3.3)$$

(a) Longitudinal profile

(b) Transversal profile

Figure 3.10: Outlet velocity profiles for Inconel, hot side: 20 g/s

Variations of the Fanning friction factor (calculated by using 3.3) with respect to Reynolds number for each channel and comparison with the correlation of Manglik [3] are given in Figure 3.14.

As observed in Figure 3.14, it can be said there is certain amount of deviation of fanning friction factor for each channel of each sample, which is always larger at cold side. It is clearly visible that for each inlet temperature, fanning factor exhibits different characteristics. In addition for similar same inlet temperatures and Reynolds numbers, fanning factor changes slightly caused by the changes of Reynolds number of other channel. Normally, it is not expected to observe change in momentum transfer of one stream with respect to the Reynolds numbers in other channel. This change is directly related with the effect of temperature on the thermophysical properties. Moreover, it means momentum transfer and heat transfer are strongly coupled in the CHX samples of interest. Addition to the findings related with experimental results, it should be mentioned that for each side at each sample, fanning factor is higher than what correlation from literature suggests. This is mainly related with two different reasons. Initially,

Figure 3.11: Pressure drop measurement for each channel.

given correlation is derived for conventionally produced CHX designs. Since additively manufactured CHX samples have higher surface roughness, it is expected to observe more pressure loss and fanning factor compared to the correlations. Second, a correlation for offset chevron fins haven't been encountered in literature. Thus, fanning friction factor correlations for offset strip fins are preferred since it is the closest fin design to the CHX samples of interest.

Correlations regarding fanning friction factor are involving fin design parameters together with Reynolds number based on hydraulic diameter. For a given sample, a proper correlation for fanning factor should be able to represent momentum transfer in different conditions. Thus, effect of operating conditions and heat transfer effects should be normalized. These two effects are quantified by inlet and outlet temperatures.

In order to estimate the effect of temperature, scaling fanning factor by using operating temperature ratio is proposed in literature [4] as given below.

Figure 3.12: Normalized Pressure drops for each channel.

$$\frac{f}{f_{ref}} = \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^m \quad (3.4)$$

Based on Equation 4.19, fanning factor results are scaled by using similar scaling definition as given below.

$$\bar{f} = f \times \left(\frac{T_{inlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^m \left(\frac{T_{outlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^n \quad (3.5)$$

In the proposed scaling definition, reference temperature is taken as 20°C. Thus normalized fanning friction factor is considered as a representative for ambient conditions and results given in Figure 3.15 and Table .

Figure 3.13: Position of hot wire profiles

$$\bar{f} = f \times \left(\frac{T_{inlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^m \left(\frac{T_{outlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^n$$

Sample	Side	m	n
AS7G06	Hot Side	0.6	-0.875
	Cold Side	1.5	-0.875
IN718-1	Hot Side	0.6	-0.875
	Cold Side	1	-0.875
IN718-2	Hor Side	0.6	-0.875
	Cold Side	1.5	-0.875

Table 3.2: Details of fanning factor normalization.

As can be seen from Figure 3.15, effect of operating conditions of the channel and heat transfer along channel are normalized. Normalized fanning factor variations don't exhibit change with the Reynolds number of other channel or inlet temperature for most of the cases. For cold side of AS7G06 and IN718-1 there are several outlier measurements for the cases where liquid nitrogen utilized. Other than that, for all samples, normalized fanning factor variation have a plateau around Reynolds number of 3000 for hot side. For cold channel; obtained results are more compatible with the correlation compared to the hot side for each sample.

Table 3.2 shows that outlet temperature effect is normalized with the exponent of -0.875 at all conditions. For inlet temperature, exponent is 1.5 for cold channels and except the cold side of IN718-1 sample 0.6 for hot channel at all samples.

(a) AS7G06

(b) IN718-1

(c) IN718-2

Figure 3.14: Fanning friction factor.

(a) AS7G06

(b) IN718-1

(c) IN718-2

Figure 3.15: Normalized fanning friction factor.

Chapter 4

Thermal Characterization

This chapter will investigate the temperature measurements performed on the samples, and use these results determine their performance. The analysis will focus first on the outlet temperature profiles, then will investigate how to properly calculate the heat transfer rate. This heat transfer will be used to determine the performances through two types of analysis: the e-NTU, and the convective heat transfer.

4.1 Temperature profiles

The evolution of temperature profiles will focus on two locations; the thermocouples located in the smaller fin channel of the hot section, but also the thermocouples located in the outlet rakes. For comparison, the configuration with 30 g/s in both hot and cold sides is chosen for the three samples, together with an inlet hot temperature of 300 °C and an inlet cold ambient temperature. As shown in

Figure 4.1: Evolution of temperature inside the fins

Figure 2.15, the 6 thermocouples are located along two lines parallel to each other, and following the flow. For ease of comparison, it was decided to average the two line and display an average evolution of temperature along the sample length. The evolution for the three samples is compared in Figure 4.1, the evolution decreases linearly when traveling from the inlet to the outlet of the sample. Both AS7G06 and IN718-1 samples have very similar temperatures, with a slightly different slope, translating a slightly higher exchange for IN718-1. But a slight difference in position of the thermocouples cannot be excluded as the height of the channels is very small (3.5 mm for AS7G06 sample and 2.25 mm for IN718 samples). But the IN718-2 has a very different evolution, with a temperature very close to

ambient and an evolution less linear. This is logical as the channel was blocked by remaining powder from the manufacturing and this results proves that the blocked channel can be considered like a wall.

Figure 4.2: Evolution of temperature at the outlet of the samples

The other comparison of temperature profiles investigates the outlet temperature in the fins. Here, the profile along either the large channel for AS7G06 sample, or the middle large channel for IN718 samples has been investigated. As shown in Figure 4.2, the evolution is also linear with the sample width, due to the cross-flow nature of the sample. The linearity is well established, considering there can be slightly deviations in the position of the thermocouples along a fin channel. Another conclusion is that the outlet profiles of the hot side is still at a higher temperature than the cold outlet profiles. However starting from a temperature gradient of 280°C at inlet, the difference is here around 30 for AS7G06 and $40\text{-}50$ for IN718 samples. The difference in values between the AS7G06 and IN718 samples can be explained by different factors. First, the location of the profile is not exactly similar as the large channel for AS7G06 is a less at mid-height position as for IN718 samples as for AS7G06, there are only 2 rows of fins. Also, as it will be shown later, the performances of the samples vary slightly. Finally, while the evolution of the cold outlet profiles are very similar in both IN718 samples, there is a 20°C difference between both hot profiles. This is due to the influence of the blocked channel in IN718-2, which acts like a wall, and increases the temperature in subsequent channel.

4.2 Heat transfer rate

To be able to estimate heat transfer capabilities of the CHX samples in different conditions is the fundamental aim of aerothermal characterization. Heat transfer rate is the most important metric to calculate other performance parameters.

In this study, air is considered as ideal gas and enthalpy difference is assumed to be related with specific heat under constant pressure and temperature change. Heat transfer rates are calculated as given in Equation 4.1. The specific heats at inlet and outlet are used, as recommended by [5] and [4] when the thermal gradient, and therefore the change in specific heat is large.

$$Q = \dot{m} |(T_{inlet}c_{p,inlet} - T_{outlet}c_{p,outlet})| \quad (4.1)$$

Another key question for the determination of the heat transfer rate is which temperatures to use for the inlet and outlet. At inlet, the upstream thermocouple is used. For outlet, either the downstream thermocouple can be used, or the outlet thermocouple rake.

In Figure 4.3, heat transfer rates measured from hot and cold sides are compared. As the heat transfer rates measured from hot side, namely Q_{hot} , are higher than Q_{cold} for all samples. Even though there are uncertainty effects, this systematic behaviour (difference in between Q_{hot} and Q_{cold}) is addressed to the thermal losses. Considering the influence of the definition of T_{out} , for AS7G06, the difference between both definition is small as the average for the thermocouple rakes is done using a selection of them to allow a proper spatial averaging. As for some tests, the downstream thermocouple was not properly placed, it was decided to use the averaging of the outlet rake for this sample. With this definition, the difference between hot and cold heat transfer rates is about 10%. Concerning the IN718-1, the thermal losses are slightly higher, more around 15%. The thermocouples for this sample are always positioned on fin channels and no measurement is available in between fins, which leads to a larger scattering of the heat transfer rates and a slightly larger difference. This effect is more strongly visible in IN718-2, most probably due to the blocked channel which modifies the distribution of temperature at the hot outlet. When using the downstream thermocouple, it can be shown that the difference between hot and cold heat transfer rates becomes negligible. This is probably also due to the blocked channel, which somehow seems to reduce the thermal losses as it converts the small hot channel into a wall, therefore insulating more the hot side from the external walls. For all these reasons, it was decided to use the downstream thermocouple as outlet temperature for both the Inconel samples.

Figure 4.3: Comparison of Q_{hot} and Q_{cold}

To take into account this systematic difference between the different hot and cold heat transfer rates, the arithmetic mean of Q_{hot} and Q_{cold} is used as the representative heat transfer rate, namely Q . With this, it is aimed to avoid under predict or over predict the thermal evaluations. This approach was

followed by [6].

$$Q = \frac{Q_{hot} + Q_{cold}}{2} \quad (4.2)$$

4.3 ε -NTU analysis

One of the main analysis methods for heat exchangers is Effectiveness-NTU (ε -NTU) method. Effectiveness-NTU (ε -NTU) method is an analysis methodology for heat exchanger which requires only inlet conditions instead of variation of temperature along HEX [7]. Thus, ε -NTU analysis is preferable because it requires less intrusive temperature measurements.

Empirical relations of effectiveness and NTU are available for different HEX types and flow configurations [7]. On the other hand, given relations doesn't represent variations with respect to design variables such as geometrical parameters or fluid properties. Empirical relations for NTU and effectiveness for crossflow heat exchangers are given in Table 4.1 and Table 4.2.

Effectiveness	
Both unmixed	$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp \left[\frac{1}{C_r} NTU^{0.22} (\exp[-C_r (NTU)^{0.78}] - 1) \right]$
C_{max} (mixed)	$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{C_r} (1 - \exp [(-C_r (1 - \exp(-NTU))]))$
C_{min} (unmixed)	
C_{max} (mixed)	$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp [(-C_r^{-1} (1 - \exp(-C_r NTU)))]$
C_{min} (unmixed)	

Table 4.1: Empirical correlations for ε .

Number of Transferred Units	
C_{max} (mixed)	$NTU = -\ln \left[1 + \left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) \ln(1 - \varepsilon C_r) \right]$
C_{min} (unmixed)	
C_{max} (mixed)	$NTU = -\left(\frac{1}{C_r} \right) \ln [C_r \ln(1 - \varepsilon) + 1]$
C_{min} (unmixed)	

Table 4.2: Empirical correlations for NTU.

As can be seen from Table 4.2, there is not an explicit correlation of NTU for unmixed condition. But it implicit formulation can be derived by using the correlation for effectiveness. Derived implicit correlation is given below.

$$NTU = \left(\frac{-1}{C_r} \ln \left[1 + \frac{C_r (1 - \varepsilon)}{NTU^{0.22}} \right] \right)^{1/0.78} \quad (4.3)$$

Instead of using correlations, one can also calculate NTU and effectiveness by their definitions. Definition of the effectiveness and NTU are given in Eqn. 4.4 and Eqn. 4.5.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{Q}{Q_{max}} \quad (4.4)$$

$$NTU = \frac{UA}{\min(C)} \quad (4.5)$$

In order to calculate NTU without using correlations overall heat transfer coefficient (U) must be known. Heat transfer calculations with respect to overall heat transfer coefficient (U) for CHX modules show that heat transfer rate is proportional to the surface area density value [8].

$$Q = UA_{exc}\Delta T_{lm} = U\beta V\Delta T_{lm} \quad (4.6)$$

Since temperature difference between both domains is not uniform through the CHX elements, LMTD (Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference) definition is defined to reduce the temperature field into one scalar. Because its original definition is valid for counterflow configuration; a correction factor needs to be applied for other flow configurations depending on inlet and outlet temperatures. Definition of the LMTD is as given below.

$$\Delta T_{lm} = F \times \Delta T_{lm,CF} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\Delta T_{lm,CF} = \frac{\Delta T_{hot} - \Delta T_{cold}}{\ln(\Delta T_{hot}/\Delta T_{cold})} \quad (4.8)$$

Correction factor for LMTD is calculated by using the inlet and outlet temperatures of both hot and cold streams. Calculation of the correction factor (F) is given in equations 4.9-4.11.

$$F = f(R, P) \quad (4.9)$$

$$R = \frac{T_{hot,inlet} - T_{hot,outlet}}{T_{cold,outlet} - T_{cold,inlet}} \quad (4.10)$$

$$P = \frac{T_{cold,outlet} - T_{cold,inlet}}{T_{hot,inlet} - T_{cold,inlet}} \quad (4.11)$$

In order to define overall heat transfer coefficient (U) one can also examine by using the point of view of convective heat transfer calculations. Overall heat transfer coefficient can be expressed by using the electrical circuit analogy as given below.

$$\frac{1}{UA} = \frac{1}{U_{cold}A_{cold}} = \frac{1}{U_{hot}A_{hot}} = \frac{1}{(\eta hA)_{cold}} + R_w + \frac{1}{(\eta hA)_{hot}} \quad (4.12)$$

In the equation 4.12, It can be seen that U consists of convective and conductive thermal resistances. In above formulation, effect of fouling resistances are neglected for ideal HEX's without fouling.

ϵ -NTU analogy has a perspective related with the overall evaluation of effectiveness and performance parameters. On the other hand, convective heat transfer calculations relies on investigating the heat transfer occurrence in small scale by separating heat transfer in convection and conduction components. Even though, both calculations have different point of view, they are connected with the variable of U.

Effectiveness values are initially calculated by using the Equation 4.4 together with NTU values from Equations 4.5 and 4.6. These evaluations are purely conducted with the experimental data. In addition the correlation (for unmixed case) for ϵ from the Table 4.1 is also used. Effectiveness quantification and comparison between the experimental results with the correlation are given in Figures 4.4-4.6.

As can be seen from Figures 4.4.a-4.6.a, there are few accumulations especially visible in IN718 samples. The reason behind that, is that ratio of heat capacities are different on each accumulation. There is linear relation in between NTU and ϵ for each group. Also it is visible that, IN718 samples resulted in higher (maximum) efficiencies for similar operating conditions even though it is not possible to maintain exactly same mass flow rates and temperatures during experiments.

From Figures 4.4.b-4.6.b, it can be said that experimental results are compatible with the correlations. This also indicates that averaging the heat transfer rates for hot and cold sides is an accurate methodology to determine representative heat transfer rate. Additionally, independent from sample and operating conditions, effectiveness values are higher up to %3 than what theory suggests.

The AS7G06 sample was also tested with the initial hot and cold side inverted. As observed in Figure 4.7, the ϵ -NTU relation is greatly reduced when the sample is inverted. The right figure shows that for similar values of mass flow rate and similar initial temperature gradient, the inverted sample show a lower heat capacity and therefore effectiveness. This show that that the fin design is indeed more efficient in the original designed way.

Figure 4.4: Effectiveness quantification of AS77G06 sample: a) Experimental results of ϵ -NTU relation, b) Comparison with correlation.

Figure 4.5: Effectiveness quantification of IN718-1 sample: a) Experimental results of ϵ -NTU relation, b) Comparison with correlation.

Effectiveness is a direct measure of heat transfer and it is normalized by maximum heat transfer rate Q_{max} which only depends on inlet variables. Thus in order to characterize the thermal performance of CHX samples, effectiveness values for each measurement were characterized by parameters related with operating conditions. By doing so, it is aimed to estimate effectiveness of the CHX samples by using known values from inlet sections. Results of the effectiveness characterization for three CHX samples are summarized in Table 4.3 and comparison of correlation and experimental results are given in Figure 4.8.

$$\epsilon = k_0 \times (\dot{m}_{cold} + \dot{m}_{hot})^{k_1} \times (\max(C_{cold,inlet}, C_{hot,inlet}))^{k_2}$$

Sample	k_0	k_1	k_2	R^2	RMSE [-]	Max. error [%]
AS7G06	4.761×10^{-4}	-1.197	1.008	0.991	0.0058	0.0125
IN718-1	1.327×10^{-4}	-1.442	1.179	0.991	0.008	0.014
IN718-2	1.987×10^{-4}	-1.38	1.091	0.944	0.0155	0.031

Table 4.3: Details of characterization for ϵ .

Figure 4.6: Effectiveness quantification of IN718-2 sample: a) Experimental results of ϵ -NTU relation, b) Comparison with correlation.

Figure 4.7: Effectiveness quantification of AS7G06 sample of single vs. inverted configuration. Left: experimental results of ϵ -NTU relation. Right: effectiveness vs. total mass flow rate and maximum heat capacity

As can be seen from Table 4.3 and Figure 4.8, effectiveness for each sample can be represented by using given exponential equation. For AS7G06 and IN718 samples, derived formulations were more accurate than the ϵ correlation derived for IN718-2 sample. On the other hand, constants of given correlations (k_0 , k_1 and k_2) for Inconel samples are more similar to each other than Aluminium sample. This can be addressed to the effect of CHX material on thermal effectiveness.

To be able to estimate thermal effectiveness gives the opportunity to estimate heat transfer rates and outlet temperatures by using inlet conditions. Resulting that, estimations for heat transfer rate, and outlet temperatures for each side are shown in Figure 7.1-7.3 located in 7. It can be said that estimations for heat transfer rate and hot side outlet temperatures are accurate especially when the effects

Figure 4.8: Comparison of the characterization of ε with the experimental results.

of measurement uncertainty and numerical errors for effectiveness correlation taken into consideration. For cold side outlet temperature, estimations are having a positive shift. This issue can be addressed to the fact that representative heat transfer rate (Q) is calculated by averaging and it is always higher than heat transfer rate measured from cold side (Q_{cold}) as given in Equation 4.2.

There are three parameters related with NTU as given in Equation 4.5. Total heat exchange area is defined by the CHX design and minimum heat capacity is related with operating conditions. On the other hand, overall heat transfer coefficient is a measure of equivalent thermal resistance of the heat transfer and it is directly related with convective heat transfer at both sides. Indirect characterization of NTU is opted because heat capacity term creates additional dependency on temperature.

Since Nusselt number is a non-dimensional parameter for convective heat transfer, Correlation regarding Nusselt number based on overall heat transfer coefficient is derived with respect to Reynolds numbers for both sides. Definition of Nusselt number based on overall heat transfer coefficient is given in Equation 4.13.

$$Nu_U = \frac{UD_h}{0.5(k_{hot,in} + k_{cold,in})} \quad (4.13)$$

$$D_h = \frac{4 \times (A_{cs,hot} + A_{cs,cold})}{P_{hot} + P_{cold}} \quad (4.14)$$

Characterization of overall Nusselt number for each CHX sample have completed by using different type of function because of accuracy considerations. Correlations are given in Equations 4.15- 4.17.

$$Nu_{U,AS7G06} = a + bRe_{cold}^c Re_{hot}^d \quad (4.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Nu_{U,IN718-1} = & p_{00} + p_{10}Re_{cold} + p_{01}Re_{hot} + p_{20}Re_{cold}^2 + \\ & p_{11}Re_{cold}Re_{hot} + p_{02}Re_{hot}^2 + p_{30}Re_{cold}^3 + p_{21}Re_{cold}^2Re_{hot} \\ & + p_{12}Re_{cold}Re_{hot}^2 + p_{03}Re_{hot}^3 \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Nu_{U,IN718-2} = & a + bRe_{cold}^c Re_{hot}^d + \\ & (p_{x1}Re_{cold}^2 + p_{y1}Re_{hot}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

Comparison of proposed overall Nusselt number correlation with experimental data is presented in Figure 7.4. Statistical performance is given in Table 4.4.

Sample	R^2	RMSE
AS7G06	0.9798	0.877
IN718-1	0.9901	0.425
IN718-2	0.943	0.1242

Table 4.4: Statistical performance of proposed Nu_U correlations

As can be seen from Table 4.4, derived correlations of overall Nusselt number are able to estimate with RMSE around 0.14. Overall Nusselt number changes in between 7 and 15. Thus, derived correlations can be considered as accurate since RMSE is 1-3 % of the experimental value.

By using correlation for overall Nusselt number, NTU can be estimated as discussed before. Comparison between NTU values and estimations of NTU based on Equations 4.15-4.17 are given in Figure 7.5

Figure 7.5 shows that NTU can be estimated within 5% of error margin. For IN718 samples there is small amount of deviation related with the operating conditions. For lower values of temperature difference between inlet sections ($T_{hot,in} - T_{cold,in}$), NTU is slightly underpredicted and vice versa.

4.4 Convective Heat Transfer Calculations

Convective heat transfer characterization focuses on the thermal boundary layer and thermal resistance on each side of the CHX sample. To be able to derive convective heat transfer calculation, logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) definition for each side shall be defined. Following LMTD definition for each side from [9] have been employed and used to derive following results.

$$\Delta T_{lm} = \frac{T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}}{\ln\left(\frac{T_{surf} - T_{inlet}}{T_{surf} - T_{outlet}}\right)} \quad (4.18)$$

Representative surface temperatures are selected by using the closest thermocouples to the wall at outlet sections. Temperature measurements obtained from B5 and C12 thermocouples are selected as a representative surface temperatures.

Since heat transfer rate measurements and thermocouple measurements are related with each other, instead of using representative heat transfer rate, heat transfer rate calculated for each side is utilized. Nusselt number for each side are tried to be characterized. As a result, as same as fanning factor, Nusselt number had to be normalized because of the temperature effects on thermophysical properties. Nusselt number variations are given in Figure 4.9.

As can be seen in Figure 4.9, even if the Nusselt number is a dimensionless number regarding convective heat transfer, there is a dependency on inlet and outlet temperatures. Similar to the fanning factor, temperature based normalization is proposed by the literature [4] as given below where T_{ref} is taken as the ambient temperature (293 K).

$$\frac{Nu}{Nu_{ref}} = \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^m \quad (4.19)$$

Based on the data and the proposed normalization method from literature, below given normalization method is suggested. Results of the Nusselt number normalization is given in Table 4.5 and Figure 4.10.

$$\overline{Nu} = Nu \times \left(\frac{T_{inlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^q \left(\frac{T_{outlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^r \left(\frac{0.5(T_{inlet,1} + T_{inlet,2})}{T_{ref}} \right)^s \quad (4.20)$$

As can be seen from Figure 4.9, there were only negligible amount of deviations of Nusselt number with respect to operating conditions for AS7G06 sample. Consequently, normalization constants are selected as zero since there is no need for normalization for Nusselt number for AS7G06 sample. From given, it can be stated that, need of temperature normalization can be related to the thermal conductivity of substrate material. Since normalized Nusselt numbers exhibit trends for each side, correlation between normalized Nusselt number and Reynolds number is derived and summarized in Table 4.6.

(a) AS7G06

(b) IN718-1

(c) IN718-2

Figure 4.9: Nusselt number values for different samples.

$$\overline{Nu} = Nu \times \left(\frac{T_{inlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^q \left(\frac{T_{outlet}}{T_{ref}} \right)^r \left(\frac{0.5(T_{inlet} + T_{outlet})}{T_{ref}} \right)^s$$

Sample	Side	q	r	s
AS7G06	Hot Side	0	0	0
	Cold Side	0	0	0
IN718-1	Hot Side	-1	2	-1
	Cold Side	0	-2	2
IN718-2	Hot Side	-3.3	5	0.5
	Cold Side	0.75	-1	0.8

Table 4.5: Details of Nusselt number normalization.

$$\overline{Nu} = a \times Re^b$$

Sample	Side	a	b	R^2	RMSE
AS7G06	Hot Side	0.01219	0.9345	0.9816	0.8463
	Cold Side	0.01402	1.041	0.977	6.5686
IN718-1	Hot Side	0.001053	1.227	0.9909	0.5091
	Cold Side	0.01418	0.9637	0.9331	3.4981
IN718-2	Hot Side	0.009051	0.7916	0.8911	0.3710
	Cold Side	0.0142	0.893	0.9465	1.3485

Table 4.6: Details of Nusselt number characterization.

(a) AS7G06

(b) IN718-1

(c) IN718-2

Figure 4.10: Normalized Nusselt number.

Chapter 5

Uncertainty Analysis

There are several kinds of sources that might cause errors in measurements and may lead the researchers to wrong conclusions especially in experimental studies. There are countless reasons for errors such as unstable conditions in the experiment environment, current leakage in circuits, time-varying changes such while taking measurements, small changes in the orientation of experimental apparatus, or random errors. Thus it is not possible to eliminate all of the errors and obtain ideal measurement systems. Therefore, predicting the range of errors is required as much as presenting the results.

An uncertainty analysis should be conducted to determine the level of errors generated while measuring variables and therefore errors in defined values that are calculated by measured values. Every stage of the whole experimental study has its own uncertainty and also they can affect each other. Thus uncertainty analysis can be done in a more systematic way by investigating different stages separately.

5.1 Uncertainty of measured quantities

Measurement uncertainties are involving statistical uncertainty and systematic error contributions for measurements. For systematic part, calibration based contributions are taken into account. For statistical uncertainty, distribution of measured values in time is discussed since time averaged values are considered. Overall uncertainty is calculated as the quadratic sum of each uncertainty contribution as given below.

$$\sigma_{overall} = (RMSE^2 + \sigma_{random}^2)^{0.5} \quad (5.1)$$

5.1.1 Pressure measurements

Standard deviation of the pressure measurement history is considered an indication of the source of statistical uncertainty for pressure measurement. During uncertainty quantification mean value is subtracted from measured values. Sample measurement history and its histogram is given in Figure 5.1.

In addition to the random errors, systematic error contribution from pressure calibration is added as given in Table 2.7. Resulting that, after investigating experimental data, maximum uncertainty (in 95 % confidence interval) for pressure measurements for each port is calculated as: $\Delta_{P,cold,inlet} = \pm 55.43$ Pa, $\Delta_{P,cold,outlet} = \pm 16.31$ Pa, $\Delta_{P,hot,inlet} = \pm 114.96$ Pa and $\Delta_{P,hot,outlet} = \pm 11.665$ Pa.

5.1.2 Velocity measurements

For velocity measurements, there are several static calibration curves obtain for different ambient conditions. Maximum observed RMSE value is 0.1503 m/s in Table 2.8. Statistical error of the hot wire measurements are dependent on the turbulence intensity. Thus, overall uncertainty increases in boundary layers. Overall uncertainty of velocity measurements can be formalized as given below:

$$\sigma_{HW} = (0.1503^2 + (U_{mean} \times TI)^2)^{0.5} \quad (5.2)$$

5

Figure 5.1: Pressure measurement history with zero mean.

5.1.3 Temperature measurements

In-build calibration curve of LABview have been utilized for thermocouple measurements [2] as discussed before. Systematic error of K type thermocouple calibration is reported as $\pm 0.05C$. Sample measurement history and its histogram is given in Figure 5.3.

Overall uncertainty for temperature measurement is assumed to be same for each thermocouple and calculated as $\Delta_T = \pm 0.9244 C$.

5.1.4 Mass flow rate measurements

In the datasheet of producer, systematic uncertainty of the mass flow rate measurements are recorded as 0.2 % of the rate. Since maximum investigated mass flow rate is 45 g/s; systematic uncertainty contribution is assumed to be 0.09 g/s. On the other hand, as can be seen from 5.3, mass flow rate measurements have comparably, higher statistical uncertainties.

Overall mass flow rate uncertainties are calculated as $\Delta_{\dot{m}} = \pm 2.6970 \text{ g/s}$.

5.2 Uncertainty of Derived Variables

For the variables that derived from measurements, uncertainty of measured values exhibits propagated error. Taylor Series expansion approach is utilized to determined propagated errors.

Figure 5.2: Temperature measurement history with zero mean.

Figure 5.3: Mass flow rate measurement history with zero mean.

5.2.1 Material properties

To determine density of air, ideal gas law is utilized. Based on the uncertainties of pressure and temperature, uncertainty of density measurements are formalized as below:

$$\Delta_{\rho} = \left(\left(\frac{\Delta P}{RT} \right)^2 + \left(-1 \frac{\Delta T P}{RT^2} \right)^2 \right)^{0.5} \quad (5.3)$$

For different pressure and temperature conditions, uncertainty for density varies as well. In accordance with above mentioned equation, maximum uncertainty at density observed at high pressure and low temperature conditions. For 233.15K (-30C) and 101325Pa uncertainty of density is calculated as $\pm 4.29 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ kg/m}^3$. Relative uncertainty of density and its effect on other parameters are assumed to be negligible.

Dynamic viscosity, thermal conductivity and specific heat is dependent on temperature and determined by table look up. Their maximum uncertainty values are $\pm 3.3576 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ Pa.s}$, $\pm 5.9679 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ W/mK}$ and $\pm 0.2167 \text{ J/kgK}$. Their relative error are $\pm 0.11\%$, $\pm 0.13\%$ and $\pm 0.023\%$.

Consequently, uncertainties of density and specific heat assumed to be negligible since their relative effects on mean values are lower than 0.1 %.

5.2.2 Pressure Drop

Pressure drop is defined as the difference between inlet and outlet pressure measurements. Total uncertainty with respect to Taylor Series expansion is given as below:

$$\Delta_{\Delta P} = (\Delta_{P,inlet}^2 + \Delta_{P,outlet}^2)^{0.5} \quad (5.4)$$

Consequently, uncertainty of pressure drop is calculated as ± 55.43 and $\pm 115.55 \text{ Pa}$ for cold and hot sides, respectively.

5.2.3 Normalized Pressure Drop

Normalized pressure drop is defined by equation 3.2. Uncertainty of normalized pressure difference is calculated with given formula.

$$\Delta_{\frac{\Delta P}{\sigma}} = \left(\left(\frac{\Delta_{\Delta P}}{\sigma} \right)^2 + \left(-2 \frac{\Delta P}{\sigma^2} \right)^2 \right)^{0.5} \quad (5.5)$$

Maximum uncertainty of normalized pressure difference is calculated as ± 64.7 and $\pm 134.59 \text{ Pa}$ for cold and hot sides, respectively.

5.2.4 Fanning Friction Factor

Fanning factor is the dimensionless number for pressure drop normalized by the dynamic pressure related with the mean velocity of the channel. Equation of the fanning factor is given in equation 3.3. Hydraulic diameter and the length of the channel is measured by the CAD program thus assumed to be exact. Consequently, uncertainty contributions to fanning friction factor comes from the pressure drop and the velocity components. Effect of the density uncertainty is neglected as discussed in 5.2.1. Uncertainty of the fanning friction factor based on Taylor series expansion is given below.

$$\Delta_{f_F} = \sqrt{\left(\Delta_{\Delta P} \frac{\partial f_F}{\partial \Delta P} \right)^2 + \left(\Delta_U \frac{\partial f_F}{\partial U} \right)^2} \quad (5.6)$$

Mean velocity is calculated with the mass flow rate, density and the cross sectional area of the channel of interest. Thus it is as given below.

$$\Delta_U = \frac{\Delta_{\dot{m}}}{\rho A_{cs}} \quad (5.7)$$

The uncertainty of mean velocity is dependent on the inlet density and the cross sectional area. Consequently, it depends on the design and operating conditions. Maximum uncertainty of the mean velocity is calculated as ± 2.2824 m/s.

Consequently, uncertainty can be calculated as a function of mean velocity and pressure drop as given below.

$$\Delta_{f_F}(U, \Delta P) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_{\Delta P} D_h}{2\rho U^2 L}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_U \Delta P D_h}{-4\rho U^3 L}\right)^2} \quad (5.8)$$

5.2.5 Temperature Difference

Temperature difference uncertainty is calculated as ± 1.82 C by using below given formalization

$$\Delta_{\Delta T} = \left((\Delta_{T_1})^2 + ((-1)\Delta_{T_2})^2\right)^{0.5} \quad (5.9)$$

5.2.6 Logarithmic Temperature Difference

Logarithmic temperature difference is a function of inlet and outlet temperature difference which is used to calculate overall heat transfer coefficient and the NTU value. Uncertainty contributions of both temperature differences are taken into account in given formulation below.

$$\Delta_{\Delta T_{lm}} = \sqrt{(\Delta_{\Delta T_{inlet}} A)^2 + (-1\Delta_{\Delta T_{outlet}} A)^2} \quad (5.10)$$

where A is given as:

$$A = \left(\frac{1}{\log(\Delta T_{inlet}/\Delta T_{outlet})} - \frac{\Delta T_{inlet} - \Delta T_{outlet}}{\Delta T_{inlet} \log(\Delta T_{inlet}/\Delta T_{outlet})^2}\right) \quad (5.11)$$

5.2.7 Heat transfer

Heat transfer for each side is calculated by Equation 4.1 and then averaged by using Equation 4.2.

$$\Delta_Q = \left((\Delta_{\dot{m}} c_p \Delta T)^2 + (\dot{m} c_p \Delta_{\Delta T})^2\right)^{0.5} \quad (5.12)$$

Maximum uncertainty of heat transfer rate for hot and cold sides are calculated as ± 467 and ± 406 W. Thus, maximum uncertainty for Q_{exp} is 436.5 W.

5.2.8 Thermal Effectiveness

Thermal effectiveness is the ratio defining the heat transfer by normalizing it with ideal maximum heat transfer. Definition of thermal effectiveness is given in equation 4.4. Maximum heat transfer is described as given below.

$$Q_{max} = \min(\dot{m} c_p) \Delta T \quad (5.13)$$

Uncertainty of maximum heat transfer is same as the uncertainty of the heat transfer because their formulation is same except the minimum operator. Consequently, the uncertainty of the thermal effectiveness is calculated as given.

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon} = \left(\left(\frac{\Delta_Q}{Q_{max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{Q \Delta_{Q_{max}}}{-2Q_{max}^2}\right)^2\right)^{0.5} \quad (5.14)$$

Simplification based on thermal effectiveness definition can be applied to the before given equation. Resulting uncertainty is formulated as given.

$$\Delta_{\varepsilon} = \sqrt{1 + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{4} \frac{\Delta Q}{Q_{max}}} \quad (5.15)$$

5.2.9 Overall Heat Transfer Coefficient

Overall heat transfer coefficient is calculated by heat transfer, heat exchange area, logarithmic mean temperature difference and temperature correction factor as given in Equation 4.6. Uncertainty contributions from heat transfer and logarithmic temperature difference is accounted; As a result, uncertainty of overall heat transfer coefficient is formulated as given below.

$$\Delta_U = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta Q}{A_{exc} F \Delta T_{lm}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{\Delta T_{lm}} Q}{-2 A_{exc} F \Delta T_{lm}^2}\right)^2} \quad (5.16)$$

5.2.10 Number of Transferred Units

NTU is the ratio of the reverse of thermal resistance and the minimum of heat capacity. Formulation of NTU is given in Equation 4.5. Uncertainty of the NTU is formulated as given below.

$$\Delta_{NTU} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\Delta_U A_{exc}}{\min(C)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\Delta_{\min(C)} A_{exc}}{-2 \min(C)^2}\right)^2} \quad (5.17)$$

Chapter 6

Conclusions

This report summarizes the work done on the tasks T4.4, T4.5, and T4.6 from the WP4. These three tasks were dedicated to the measurements of the combined hot-cold channel elements.

The first task consisted in designing the facility dedicated to aerothermal measurements to be performed on combined hot-cold modules. The facility has been designed and built around March 2020. The facility consists in a cross with the horizontal section being dedicated to the cold side, while the vertical section is dedicated to the hot side. The hot side can reach 45 g/s at 300°C thanks to the IVKDF compressed air system as well as a 17kW thermal resistance. The cold side can reach 45 g/s either at ambient temperature, or at temperature as low as -30°C due to a mixing of the ambient air with liquid nitrogen. Each section consists of 1m length upstream and 0.5m length downstream the sample. The dimensions of these section are consistent with the sample dimension. All sections are insulated, except for the inlet section of the cold side. Finally, a heat exchanger is connected to the exit of the cold section to pre-heat the incoming air before entering the thermal resistance.

The second task consisted in instrumenting the modules. The facility has two vortex flow meters that allow to measure the inlet mass flowrate of each branch from 13 to 45 g/s. In addition, an innovative procedure using the pressure drop introduced by the sample allows to reach flowrates down to 5-8 g/s. Pressure and temperatures are measured at 10 hydraulic diameter upstream and 5 hydraulic diameter downstream each channel. Thermocouples at several locations in the facility are also introduced to better analyze the performances of the pre-heater for future use in the final facility. Finally, 6 thermocouples are introduced inside the sample, as well as right at the outlet of each sample side (with 14 measurement points per side).

Finally, the third task consisted in performing the experimental tests on the hot-cold modules. Originally 4 modules were planned; 2 in Inconel and 2 in Aluminium. However, the design work showed no substantial improvement of evolutive fin designs in Aluminum so it was decided to test only one sample in this material. Therefore, a total of 3 samples: AS7G06, IN718-1 and IN718-2 were printed and tested. In terms of manufacturing, the Aluminum sample had slight deformations on the flange, and a few damaged fins, most probably due to the de-supporting. The first Inconel sample IN718-1 had less flange deformation (might be due to an increased thickness), and good final results for the fins, as the design was modified to improve the manufacturing, *i.e.* slightly larger fin thickness and rounded fins top and bottom. However, during de-supporting, one of the walls was cut on one of the outlet side. It was decided then to fill the space with thermal paste. Finally, the third sample IN718-2 had no problem in the flanges neither in the fins. However, the small channel on the hot side, due to the printing direction, could not be properly de-powdered and was ultimately blocked. This will strongly affect the results.

The analysis of the results was divided in two parts: the aeraulic and the thermal characterization. The aeraulic first focused on the inlet and outlet velocity profiles for the three samples. The analysis of the inlet profiles show that the flow is almost symmetric with a slight asymmetry on the hot side

most probably coming from the upstream bend. Several flow rates were measured, and the influence of the upstream length on the profiles showed that 1 m is necessary. These conclusions are valid for both Aluminum and Inconel inlet flows, as the size of the inlet channel was different for each material. The analysis of the velocity profiles at the outlet of the samples showed an increased turbulence intensity generated by the flow passing in the fins. Also, the averaged velocity profile is now reflecting the passage through the different fin channels, especially on the transverse profile. The blocked channel on the IN718-2 was confirmed. The analysis of the pressure drop generated by the samples lead to several conclusions. First, the evolution with mass flow rate follow a typical second order polynomial. The pressure is higher in the hot side as the fins for that side are more dense and of lower height. Higher pressure drops were also found in Inconel samples compared to Aluminum, also due to the fin design. In addition, the blocked channel from IN718-2 increased the hot side pressure drop for this sample. Temperature dependency of the pressure drop was observed, and found to be related with the dynamic viscosity at inlet section. By doing related normalization, temperature dependency is eliminated. Furthermore, a precise correlation for normalized pressure drops as second order polynomial relation with respect to mass flow rate is proposed. This characterization enables to estimate pressure drop at different operating conditions in the range of experimental matrix for each CHX sample. Finally, Fanning friction factor exhibits strong dispersion especially at cold side. Important remark is that, fanning factor is affected by heat transfer in addition to the operating temperature. Thus, not only inlet temperature but also outlet temperature is considered during normalization to represent heat transfer in addition to operating conditions. Normalized fanning factors show that fanning factors are higher than the Manglik correlation for standard offset-strip fins. This is highly related with the higher surface roughness compared to the conventionally produced CHX's but also due to the influence of the design.

The second part of the analysis was dedicated to the thermal characterization. First, the analysis of the temperature profiles inside the small hot channel showed a linear evolution through the sample, as well as confirmed that the blocked channel can be therefore considered as a wall. The analysis of the outlet temperature profiles also showed a linear evolution along the width, due to the cross-flow nature of the sample. Then, discussions on the proper estimation of the heat transfer rate was needed. The strong temperature gradient justified the use of the inlet and outlet heat capacities. Also, the choice for the outlet temperature was discussed for each sample. The choice for the position of thermocouples at the outlet sections were focused on the fins temperature evaluation, which lead to overestimation of the average temperature. In future work, a more systematic evaluation of the outlet temperature might lead to more precise results. In the view of the journal publication concerning this work, the influence of the averaging from the thermocouple rake will be assessed by comparison with the numerical simulations performed by Themisth.

As already observed for the pressure drop, conjugate heat transfer and fluid flow in CHX passages are highly dependent on operating conditions. Temperature dependency of the thermophysical properties cause variations on all parameters independent from if the parameter is dimensional or dimensionless. In addition, due to the coupled behaviour of heat and momentum transfer, mass flow rate of one side is able to affect the momentum transfer parameters of the other side. Thermal effectiveness of the CHX samples are calculated experimentally and results are compared with correlations from the theory. Even though there is a difference up to 4% in favor of experiments, results are mostly close to the correlations in uncertainty levels. Thermal effectiveness have been characterized precisely based on mass flow rates and thermal capacities. Resulting that, heat transfer rate, hot side outlet temperature and cold side outlet temperature can be estimated. Even if estimations regarding outlet temperatures are not accurate as expected; Proposed correlation of thermal effectiveness enables to estimate heat transfer rate at different operating conditions. Overall heat transfer rate is non-dimensionalized by using Nusselt number definition and then characterized. For each CHX sample, different models have proposed. Resulting that, NTU of heat transfer can be estimated. Convective heat transfer evaluation for each side is conducted by investigating Nusselt number and its variation with Reynolds number. After temperature normalization consisting of inlet temperature, outlet temperature and inlet temperature of the other channel; correlations for normalized Nusselt numbers are derived. Both thermal effectiveness and normalized Nusselt number

correlations were more accurate at hot side than cold side. This can be addressed to the aggressive change of thermophysical properties at lower temperatures. It should be stated that, investigations regarding convective heat transfer at each side shows the need to measure surface temperature. Thus, for further studies, it is suggested to implement thermocouples to accurately measure the surface temperature at inlet sections and outlet sections.

Bibliography

- [1] Alfa LAVAL how plate heat exchangers work. <https://www.alfalaval.my/products/heat-transfer/plate-heat-exchangers/gasketed-plate-and-frame-heat-exchangers/heat-exchanger/how-plate-heat-exchanger-work/>. Accessed: 2021-04-26
- [2] D. Potter, Measuring Temperature with Thermocouples – a Tutorial. Tech. rep., National Instruments (1996)
- [3] R.M. Manglik, A.E. Bergles. Heat Transfer and Pressure Drop Correlations for the Rectangular Offset Strip Fin Compact Heat Exchanger (1995)
- [4] W. Kays, A. London, *Compact heat exchangers* (Krieger Pub. Co., 1984)
- [5] T. Lestina, K. Bell, in *Advances in heat transfer*, vol. 35 (Elsevier, 2001), pp. 1–55
- [6] R. Shah, S. Zhou, in *Proceedings of the international conference on compact heat exchangers for the process industries* (1997), pp. 365–379
- [7] F.P. Incropera, D.P. DeWitt, *Fundamentals of Heat and Mass Transfer*, 6th edn. (John Wiley Sons, Inc., New York City, New York)
- [8] J. Hesselgreaves, *Compact Heat Exchangers: Selection, Design and Operation*. January (Elsevier Science & Technology Books, 2001)
- [9] C. Stimpson, J. Snyder, K. Thole, D. Mongillo, (2015). DOI 10.1115/GT2015-43940

Chapter 7

Appendix

(a) Heat transfer rate

(b) $T_{hot,outlet}$

(c) $T_{cold,outlet}$

Figure 7.1: Thermal estimations based of effectiveness correlation for AS7G06 sample.

(a) Heat transfer rate

(b) $T_{hot,outlet}$

(c) $T_{cold,outlet}$

Figure 7.2: Thermal estimations based of effectiveness correlation for IN718-1 sample.

(a) Heat transfer rate

(b) $T_{hot,outlet}$

(c) $T_{cold,outlet}$

Figure 7.3: Thermal estimations based of effectiveness correlation for IN718-2 sample.

Figure 7.4: Comparison of the characterization of Nu_U with the experimental results.

(a) AS7G06

(b) IN718-1

(c) IN718-2

Figure 7.5: Comparison of NTU estimations based on Nu_U correlations with NTU values.